

The **VIRTIGATION project** aims to protect tomatoes and cucurbits in Europe and the Mediterranean. Together with partners from EU neighbouring areas – Morocco, Israel and India – VIRTIGATION develops **bio-based solutions to safeguard tomatoes and cucurbits from emerging viral diseases.**

Specifically, VIRTIGATION addresses emerging viral diseases caused by the **begomovirus ToLCNDV** (Tomato leaf curl New Delhi Virus, transmitted by whiteflies) **and the tobamovirus ToBRFV** (Tomato brown rugose fruit virus, mechanically transmitted).

High-Potential Project Result

- VIRTIGATION partner Volcani Center developed new sanitation protocols to eradicate ToBRFV-infections in tomato plants
- Their extreme acidic and alkaline solutions can significantly reduce the infectious potential of the ToBRFV tobamovirus
- Their new sanitation protocols were published in the *Plant Soil* journal:
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-024-06690-y>

High-Potential Project Result

- VIRTIGATION partner LIST investigated the role of climate change on the biology and spread of ToLCNDV and its whitefly vector
- Their findings indicate a strong influence of future climate conditions in the acquisition efficiency of the ToLCNDV begomovirus
- The **ToLCNDV whitefly vector, the *Bemisia tabaci* (MED)** benefits from increased ToLCNDV inoculation efficiency in a hotter climate

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RTDS Group

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